

PACKAGE OF PRACTICES FOLLOWED ON GAUSHALAS OF JALNA AND AURANGABAD DISTRICTS

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(MS Received: 26.11.2023; MS Revised: 30.12.2023; MS Accepted: 02.01.2024)

MS 3157

(RESEARCH PAPER IN ANIMAL HUSBANDRY AND DAIRY SCIENCE)

Abstract

The study was conducted in Jalna and Aurangabad district with a view to find out the adoption of improved package of practices followed by the Gaushalas. Data was collected from 40 gaushalas belonging to Jalna and Aurangabad district with the help of structured interview schedule containing questionnaire about improved package of practices, through personal interview technique. The 68 per cent of small and 46 per cent of medium sized Gaushalas belonged to high adoption category. Majority (75 %) in large, followed by 54 per cent in medium and 32 per cent in small sized Gaushalas had medium level of adoption category. While 25 per cent of the large gaushalas belonged to low adoption category.

Keywords: Adoption practices, gaushalas, Jalna, Aurangabad.

Introduction

The total livestock population is 535.78 million in the country during 2020- 21 showing increase of 4.8% over livestock census 2012. The total number of cattle in the country is 192.49 million in 2020 – 21 showing an increase of 0.8 % over previous census. There is a decline of 6 % in the total indigenous (both descript and non-descript) cattle population over the previous census. The stray cattle population in India is about 5 million which is over and above the 193 million cattle present in the country. The census further trends the population of stray cattle show marginal decrease of about 3.2% over the previous census but the figure still hovers around 5 million which is worrisome. (Anonymous 2020-21) [1]. According to the Bureau of Indian Standards, a gaushala is a protective shelter, abode, or sanctuary for cows, set up to improve their health and life, sell pure milk products, conserve germplasm, and stop animal cruelty (BIS, 1987) [4]. The origin of gaushalas can be traced to the Vedic period, where the emphasis was on protection, preservation and development of cows. In the present day, gaushalas are the only institutions providing care and shelter to stray, abandoned and 'unproductive' bovines. (FIAPO, 2019) [6].

Material and Methods

A field survey was conducted to collect the information on various package of practices followed by Gaushala owners in Jalna and

$$\text{Level of adoption} = \frac{\text{Total score obtained by the respondents}}{\text{Maximum possible score}} \times 100$$

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained from survey was analyzed statistically by using suitable methods. The collected data were classified and tabulated in order to measure the objectives of the study. Based on the nature of the study, the tabulated data were analyzed statistically with the help of the explained statistical methods

Frequency

This was used to find out the number of respondents in each cell.

Percentage

The percentage value was calculated to make simple comparisons. Percentage value was calculated by dividing the frequency in the particular cell by number of respondents and multiplies it by 100.

$$\text{Percentage (P)} = \frac{n}{N} \times 100$$

Where,

n= Frequency of particular cell

N= Total number of the respondents in a particular cell.

Mean

The Arithmetic average of the set of data had to be often computed during the analysis of data. This measurement was used to see the central tendency of the data. The mean score of a series of data was

Aurangabad district of Maharashtra. The data were recorded during a period of 1 March 2023 to 31 June 2023 by using pretested interview schedule, interview guide and direct observations method.

Adoption of Good Management Practices (GMPs) by Gaushalas

Adoption is the mental process through which an individual passes from hearing about an innovation for the first time to the final adoption (Rogers, 1995) [9]. Good Management Practices was operationally defined as the degree to which a respondent actually adopts a practice for the purpose of measurement of extent of adoption of GMP in their Gaushalas at the time of investigation and it was determined by a simple schedule developed by the investigator. The practices were classified into six categories namely, breeding, feeding healthcare, general management, clean milk production and animal welfare practices. There were two columns representing 'adopted', and 'not adopted' with weightage of 1 and 0 respectively. The minimum and maximum score a respondent could get on this scale. The total score obtained by Gaushalas was calculated and with the help of following formula their adoption level for various practices and overall adoption level was calculated. According to the score value, the Gaushalas were divided into three groups' namely low, medium and high adoption level based on mean and standard deviation.

equal to the sum of individual measures divided by the total number of respondents. The mean scores for each group were worked out by computing with this formula.

$$X = \frac{\sum X_i}{N}$$

Where,

X= Mean

$\sum X_i$ = Sum of each of the individual, measurement of the scores.

N= Number of respondents.

Result and Discussion**Adoption level of Gaushala in breeding practices**

From the table no 1, reported that the large majority (88 %) in case of large Gaushalas, followed by 62 per cent of medium sized Gaushalas and 63 per cent of small sized Gaushalas adopted detection of heat. The majority (88 %) in case of large sized Gaushalas, followed by 85 % in medium and 79 % in small sized Gaushalas adopted breeding through N.S/A.I. A large majority (74%) of small sized Gaushalas adopted 'pregnancy diagnosis by veterinarian' as compared to 62 per cent in medium and 75 per cent by large sized Gaushalas. The pregnancy detection by external signs in small gaushalas 32%, medium gaushalas 38% and large gaushalas 25%.

Table 1: Distribution of Gaushalas according to their adoption level in breeding practices

Sr. No.	Breeding Practices	Small		Medium		Large	
		Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)
1	Detection of heat	12 (63%)	7 (37%)	8 (62%)	5 (38%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
2	Breeding through N.S/A.I.	15 (79%)	4 (21%)	11 (85%)	2 (15%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
3	Insemination of dairy cattle within 12-18 hrs. of onset of estrus	11 (58%)	8 (42%)	7 (54%)	6 (46%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)
4	Pregnancy diagnosis by veterinarian	14 (74%)	5 (26%)	8 (62%)	5 (38%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)
5	Pregnancy detection by external signs	6 (32%)	13 (68%)	5 (38%)	8 (62%)	2 (25%)	6 (75%)

The detection of heat in small gaushalas 12 per cent, medium 8 per cent and large gaushalas 7 per cent breeding through N.S/A.I. followed 15% in small gaushalas, 11% in medium and 7% in large gaushalas.

The present trend of the result were in agreement with results reported Chandra and Kambhoj (2019) [5] indicated that, nearly half (46.67%) of the Gaushalas used selected bull for breeding purpose, meanwhile 43.33 per cent of Gaushalas used non-selected bull; and only 10 per

cent of Gaushalas used either, selected or non-selected bull for breeding purpose in Haryana. They also revealed that, 33.33 per cent of Gaushalas in Haryana followed AI practice for breeding purpose. Sharma *et al.* (2020) [10] reported management of cow shelter in India. The majority of the shelters (91%) allowed the cows to reproduce; 44% of which was mating by bulls housed with the cows and 44% was planned, with cows taken to bulls when oestrus was observed.

Adoption level of Gaushala in feeding practices

Table 2: Distribution of Gaushalas according to their adoption level in feeding practices

(n= 40)

N O	Feeding Practices	Small		Medium		Large	
		Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)
1	Cultivation of green fodder crops	13 (68%)	6 (32%)	9 (69%)	4 (31%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)
2	Stall feeding or semi-stall feeding	11 (58%)	8 (42%)	10 (77%)	3 (33%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
3	Feeding of extra ration during pregnancy	13 (68%)	6 (32%)	11 (85%)	2 (15%)	8 (100%)	0 (20%)
4	Preparation and feeding of silage	2 (11%)	17 (89%)	4 (31%)	19 (69%)	4 (50%)	4 (50%)
5	Dipping of concentrate feed in water one hour before feeding	10 (53%)	9 (47%)	8 (62%)	5 (38%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)
6	Provision for mineral mixture powder	6 (32%)	13 (68%)	5 (38%)	8 (62%)	3 (38%)	5 (62%)
7	Milch animals fed with extra concentrate feed @ 1kg to 2.5kg	14 (74%)	5 (26%)	10 (77%)	3 (33%)	8 (100%)	0 (30%)

From table no 2, it was show that the cultivation of green fodder crops in small sized gaushalas 68 %, medium 69 %, and large sized 75 %. All the large sized Gaushalas (100.00%), followed by majority (85%) in medium sized Gaushalas and small sized Gaushalas (68%) adopted feeding of extra ration during pregnancy for equitable supply of balanced ration of feed and fodder to the cattle. Majority (88.00 %) in large sized Gaushalas, followed by 77.00 per cent in medium sized Gaushalas and 58.00 per cent in small sized Gaushalas adopted stall feeding practices. The silage was prepared in less quantity in every gaushalas i.e. 11 % in small, 31 % in medium, 50 % in large gaushalas. The milch animals fed with extra concentrate feed @ 1kg to 2.5kg in small gaushalas 74 %, medium gaushalas 77 % and 100 % in large sized gaushalas.

Adoption level of Gaushalas in healthcare practices

Table 3: Distribution of Gaushalas according to their adoption level in healthcare practices

(n= 40)

Sr. No.	Healthcare Practices	Small		Medium		Large	
		Adopted Frequency (%)	Non-Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non-Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non-Adopted Frequency (%)
1	Vaccination against HS/FMD/BQ disease before onset of monsoon	14 (74%)	5 (26%)	11 (85%)	2 (15%)	8 (100%)	0 (0%)
2	Treatment of sick animal by veterinarian	9 (47%)	10 (53%)	9 (69%)	3 (31%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
3	Isolation of sick animal from the herd	12 (63%)	7 (37%)	8 (61%)	5 (39%)	8 (100%)	0 (0%)
4	Deworming of cattle	11 (58%)	8 (42%)	8 (62%)	5 (38%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)

From table no 3, it was indicated that the vaccination practice adopted in large scale in all the gaushalas i.e. in small gaushalas 74%, medium gaushalas 85% and large gaushalas 100%.

A large majority (88%) in large sized Gaushalas, followed by medium sized (69%) Gaushalas and in small (47 %) adopted treatment of sick animals by veterinarian. A large majority (100%) in large sized Gaushalas, followed by small sized Gaushalas (63%) and medium sized gaushalas (61%) adopted 'Isolation of sick animal from the herd'. The deworming of cattle was followed large scale in large sized gaushalas 75%, in medium sized gaushalas 62% and in small sized 58%.

The similar result of present findings were Gunaseelan *et al.* (2018) [7] reported a large majority (77.50 %) of the dairy farmers adopted the practice of deworming in calves and 65.00 per cent of them vaccinated their animals against contagious diseases.

Mandi *et al.* (2018) [8] reported the animal health care and fertility

Table 4: Distribution of Gaushalas according to their adoption level in general management practices

(n= 40)

Sr. No.	General Management Practices	Small		Medium		Large	
		Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)
1	Provision of sufficient ventilation in cattle shed	13 (68%)	6 (32%)	11 (85%)	2 (15%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)
2	Weaning of calf	15 (79%)	4 (21%)	7 (54%)	5 (46%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
3	Daily cleaning of cattle shed before milking	19 (100%)	0 (0%)	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	8 (100%)	0 (0%)
4	Record maintenance	19 (100%)	0 (0%)	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	8 (100%)	0 (0%)
5	Milking of dairy cattle at fixed time	17 (89%)	2 (11%)	10 (77%)	3 (23%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
6	Provide sufficient clean and fresh water to cattle.	19 (100%)	0 (0%)	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	8 (100%)	0 (0%)

The findings were in line with the findings of Gunaseelan *et al.* (2018) [7] reported the practice of 'feeding of green and dry fodder, a larger proportion (87.50 %) of the farmers adopted it. An overwhelming majority (90.00 %) of the large farmers adopted the practice 'feeding of concentrate mixture on the basis of milk production' followed by medium (76.92 %) and small (44.26 %) farmers.

Ashokbabu *et al.* (2020) [2] reported that majority of respondents (55.0%) sent their animals for grazing and In case of feeding of milch animals majority of the farmers were following group feeding (94.17 %). It was observed that 80.0 percent of respondents fed their animals only with paddy straw as dry fodder and rest of the respondents fed a combination of paddy, jowar and maize straws (20.0 %).

should be taken care of by Veterinary Dispensary. The dispensary should have the facility for first aid, vaccination, artificial insemination, de-worming etc.

Adoption level of Gaushalas in general management practices

All the Gaushalas (100%) adopted daily cleaning of cattle shed before milking, record maintenance, provide sufficient clean and fresh water to cattle, care of new born calf. In all sizes of Gaushalas, large majority of them provided 'provision of sufficient ventilation in cattle shed' i.e. medium (85 %) sized Gaushalas, followed by 75 per cent in large and 68 per cent in small sized gaushalas. The large majority in large sized Gaushalas (88 %) in small sized Gaushalas (79 %) and most of medium sized (54 %) the adopted 'provision of sufficient ventilation in cattle shed'. The disinfection of animal shed every week by disinfectant was followed by small sized gaushalas 74 %, medium sized gaushalas 69 % and in large sized 63 %.

7	Disinfection of animal shed every week by disinfectant	14 (74%)	5 (26%)	9 (69%)	4 (31%)	5 (63%)	3 (37%)
8	Care of new born calf	19 (100%)	0 (0%)	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	8 (100%)	0 (0%)

The similar findings with present result Simul *et al.* (2012) [11] presented the available baseline data on Red Chittagong cattle management practices. Tin and Chatai were used by about 26.19 per cent of the respondents to construct cattle houses. A total of 81 per cent of the cow house had adequate ventilation and lighting.

Adoption level of Gaushalas in clean milk production practices

It is inferred from the table no 5, that majority (88 %) in large sized

Gaushalas, followed by 77 per cent in medium and 74 per cent in small sized Gaushalas adopted 'cleaning of udder with clean water & antiseptic solution before milking'. The 63% per cent in large sized Gaushalas, followed by majority 62 per cent in medium and 79 per cent in small sized Gaushalas practiced adoption of 'full hand method of milking' as it was perceived and recommended as the right method of milking by majority of large sized Gaushalas.

Table 5: Distribution of Gaushalas according to their adoption level in clean milk production (n= 40)

Sr. No.	Clean Milk Practices	Small		Medium		Large	
		Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)	Non Adopted Frequency (%)	Adopted Frequency (%)
1	Cleaning of udder with clean water & antiseptic solution before milking	14 (74%)	5 (26%)	10 (77%)	3 (33%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
2	Practicing full hand method of milking	15 (79%)	4 (21%)	8 (62%)	5 (38%)	5 (63%)	3 (27%)
3	Using of clean utensils for milking	16 (84%)	3 (16%)	11 (85%)	2 (15%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)
4	Washing of milker hand with soap/ antiseptic solution before milking	9 (47%)	10 (53%)	9 (69%)	4 (31%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)
5	Personal hygiene while milking	13 (68%)	6 (32%)	7 (54%)	6 (46%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)

The use of clean utensils for milking in large sized gaushalas 88 %, followed by medium sized 85 % and small sized gaushalas 84 %. The washing of milker hand with soap/antiseptic solution before milking followed by 47 % in small sized gaushalas, 69 % in medium sized gaushalas and 75 % in large sized gaushalas. Personal hygiene while milking was largely followed in large sized 88 %, followed by small sized 68 % and medium sized 54 %.

The comparable findings with present study as Bimal and Kumar (2013) [3] reported the majority (73.33 %) of dairy farmers were following full hand method, 18.33 per cent and 8.33 per cent were following knuckling and machine milking respectively as method of

milking. About 68.33 % of dairy farmers were practicing udder massaging and feeding concentrate and 31.66 per cent were practicing calf suckle reflex for letdown of the milk

Overall adoption level of Gaushalas in good management practices

The table no. 6 revealed that the exactly of 68 per cent of small and 46 per cent of medium sized gaushalas belonged to high adoption category. Majority (75 %) in large, followed by 54 per cent in medium and 32 per cent in small sized Gaushalas had medium level of adoption category. while 25 per cent of the large Gaushalas belonged to low adoption category.

Table 6: Distribution of Gaushalas according to their overall adoption level in good management practices (n= 40)

Sr. No.	Adoption categories	Small		Medium		Large	
		Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent	Frequency	Per cent
1	Low (up to 4)	0	0	0	0	2	25
2	Medium (5 to 9)	6	32	7	54	6	75
3	High (above 9)	13	68	4	46	0	0
	Total	19	100	13	100	8	100

Conclusion

The study revealed that the overall extent of adoption of improved animal husbandry practices in the study area was found to be 68 per cent of small and 46 per cent of medium sized gaushalas belonged to high adoption category. Majority (75 %) in large, followed by 54 per cent in medium and 32 per cent in small sized Gaushalas had medium level of adoption category. while 25 per cent of the large Gaushalas belonged to low adoption category.

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